

7th European Congress of Pharmacology

EPHAR2016

Military Museum and Cultural Center
June 26-30 2016, İstanbul, TURKEY
www.ephar2016.org

Congress
Book

Welcome

Dear friends and colleagues,

It is a great pleasure for me to welcome you to Istanbul, Turkey for the 7th European Congress of Pharmacology in 26-30 June 2016. The Congress is hosted by the Turkish Pharmacological Society. The members of the society, the Local Organising Committee and the Scientific Committee took great care to design a programme that combines hot topics in pharmacology. All the announcements are available through the congress web page www.epharm2016.org. After the congress the website will be accessed from www.tfd.org.tr/epharm/2016 in order to make it available for long term.

Turkish Pharmacological Society, established in 1966, is a rapidly expanding community looking forward to having international scientific and social collaborations. Our 23rd national meeting, held in Ankara between 7-10 September 2015 welcomed more than 300 delegates. 2016 will be 50th anniversary of our society, and it is going to be a great pleasure for us to celebrate both events together in Istanbul.

The 7th European Congress of Pharmacology is taking place in Military Museum and Cultural Centre, located in the heart of the city. This modern congress centre with easy transportation offers convenient facilities such as meeting rooms for ongoing parallel sessions allowing you to select your favourite topics, exhibition hall for poster sessions and companies, and networking places to meet with your colleagues.

Istanbul is the biggest city in Turkey, located in the north-western part of the country, with a pleasant climate in June. Istanbul is a real must see destination with many unique features, easily accessible by hundreds of direct flights from many countries. It is the only city in the world to connect two continents-Europe and Asia. Istanbul, which has been a capital for centuries, embraces many historical and cultural beauties of Turkey including ancient and modern attractions.

On behalf of the Organising Committee, I welcome you to Istanbul for a great meeting to exchange knowledge between basic and clinical fields of pharmacology throughout the World and to share good times.

We hope EPHAR 2016 Istanbul will always be in your best memories!

Öner SÜZER
Congress Chair EPHAR 2016

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P263: The effects of ursodeoxycholic acid on cytotoxic activity and proapoptotic potential of doxorubicin in MCF-7 cell line

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Doxorubicin (Dox) is one of the most commonly used antineoplastic agents; however, serious dose-dependent toxicity-related events limit its use. Therefore, the enhancement of Dox function along with reducing dose-dependent undesirable effects is one of the main challenges in developing novel Dox formulations. Due to an amphipathic structure, bile acids (Bas) promote transport of various substances through biological membranes, influencing their physiological and pharmacological activity. The discovery that Bas act as signaling molecules which regulate cell metabolism and fate on a systemic level, raised complexity of Bas function. The aim of this study was to determine an effect of ursodeoxycholic acid (Udca) on the cytotoxic activity and proapoptotic potential of Dox *in vitro*, in a model of human breast adenocarcinoma.

Cytotoxic activities of Dox and Udca, used as single agent or in combinations, were determined using MTT assay. The quantitative analysis of expression of genes involved in apoptosis, Bax and Bcl-2, was assessed using RT-qPCR method. Gene expression was calculated using $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method and normalized to β -actin.

Both Dox and Udca expressed dose-dependent cytotoxic activity with IC_{50} values of 0.64 μM and 320.5 μM , respectively. Co-treatment with Dox and physiologically relevant concentration of Udca significantly increased cytotoxicity compared to Dox alone ($p < 0.05$). The mRNA expression of a pro-apoptotic Bax was significantly increased ($p < 0.01$) in both Dox-treated and Udca-co-treated groups compared to control, 3.22- and 2.28-fold, respectively. Bcl-2 mRNA expression was 1.42 fold higher in Dox-treated cells ($p < 0.01$), whereas 1.25 fold decreased in co-treated cells ($p < 0.01$). Also, Bax/Bcl-2 ratio was higher in group of co-treated cells than in Dox-treated cells.

Udca modulates cytotoxic activity of Dox and increases susceptibility of MCF-7 cells to undergo mitochondrial-mediated apoptosis, indicating that Udca may act as potential chemo-sensitizing agent.

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